

ISOLATION, CHARACTERIZATION, AND UTILIZATION OF ACETIC ACID BACTERIA FROM DIFFERENT VINEGAR MANUFACTURERS IN THE PROVINCE OF LA UNION, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the role of pure culture *Acetobacter* species in enhancing and speeding up vinegar production is essential for economic growth. The study sought to acquire sugarcane vinegar product samples from La Union, assess the physicochemical characteristics of these samples, isolate potential *Acetobacter* species, characterize the *Acetobacter* isolates based on morphological, biochemical, and physiological traits, screen the isolates using the Potency Index determination, and evaluate the effectiveness of the *Acetobacter* isolates in producing vinegar with a 5% inoculum using a fermented brown sugar solution. The research study employed descriptive-quantitative research. Five sugarcane vinegar samples from the towns of Naguilian, Luna, and Agoon were collected and assessed for their physicochemical characteristics. Physicochemical analysis of sugarcane vinegar samples showed that SV1 has the most sugar, followed by SV3, SV5, SV4, and SV2. Six *Acetobacter* species were isolated from the samples with a clearing zone. *Acetobacter* species were confirmed by their rod-shaped structure, Gram-negative, catalase positivity, and oxidase negativity. Despite growing on two percent sodium acetate, ethanol, and glucose above the GYC medium formulation, the isolates survived. The isolated *Acetobacter* species can grow at 25-40°C and pH 3-8. After four days of incubation, Isolate f had the highest Potency Index of 4.05 and the

highest vinegar production potential of six isolates. In terms of average pH levels and titratable acidity, the *Acetobacter* acetic acid fermentation setups exhibited elevated percentages, achieving 5.0% acidity after one month. The six *Acetobacter* isolates are highly recommended for acetic acid vinegar fermentation to increase vinegar production in one month.

Keywords: *Acetobacter, Sugarcane Vinegar, Titrable Acidity, Potency Index, GYC Medium*

INTRODUCTION

Vinegar is a solution with a 5% concentration of acetic acid. It is produced through alcoholic fermentation using sweet ingredients (Joyeux et al., 1984; Drysdale & Fleet, 1985; Kocher et al., 2006). According to Cruess, in 1958, the word “vinegar” originated from the French terms “Vin” (wine) and “Aigre” (sour), both of which indicate a sour taste. Vinegar was historically used for food preservation. It is a liquid solution made for human consumption. Also, it is produced from agricultural raw materials containing starch and sugar through a two-step fermentation process. The first step is alcoholic fermentation, followed by acetous fermentation, as defined by Codex Alimentarius (1987) and according to Solieri and Giudici (2009), alcoholic fermentation in fruits, cereals, and vegetables played a crucial role in developing vinegar in agriculture. Vinegar is a multifunctional liquid employed as a seasoning and a component in the manufacturing of certain food items. The acidic taste of vinegar is primarily due to its main component, acetic acid.

Sugarcane vinegar is a type of vinegar that is produced by fermenting ethanol in liquid derived from sugarcane (Fresco, 2011). Cane vinegar, also called “Sukang Iloko” in the Northern Ilocos Region, is one of the most well-known goods in the Philippines. It is produced from the juice of sugarcane. Although there is no residual sugar, contrary to expectations, it is not sweeter than other vinegar. Conversely, it has a color ranging from golden brown to deep yellow and a subtle taste reminiscent of rice vinegar but with a more invigorating quality. Even though “sukang maasim” is merely a broad term that means “sour vinegar,” it is usually referred to as such in the Philippines (Fresco, 2011).

Acetic Acid Bacteria (AAB) are heterogeneous group of Gram-negative bacteria recognized for their capacity to efficiently and incompletely oxidize a wide range of carbon sources, particularly sugars and alcohols. Certain strains of AAB are utilized for commercial vinegar production and thrive in oxygen-rich environments (Adachi et al., 2003). According to Sokollek et al. (1998) and Kadere et al. (2008), *Acetobacter* species can convert ethanol, sugar alcohols, and sugars into various organic acids through aerobic fermentation, also known as oxidative fermentation.

According to Gomes et al. (2018), vinegar is made industrially through acetic acid fermentation, typically an oxidative fermentation. *Acetobacter* strains are the most common acetic acid bacteria employed in the industrial manufacturing of vinegar because the solution is a crucial component of food products, the preservation process, and

condiments. The food sectors that use vinegar understand the value of *Acetobacter* species in the industrial sector well.

Oxidation refers to the chemical process of introducing oxygen to a substance while simultaneously experiencing a reduction in hydrogen or electrons. Ethanol undergoes a two-step oxidation process. The initial stage involves the transformation of ethanol into acetaldehyde. Furthermore, the process involves the oxidation of acetaldehyde to generate acetic acid, as Ning et al. (2017) stated. Under the influence of *Acetobacter* species, ethanol undergoes conversion into acetic acid, leading to vinegar production. This process can occur with many alcoholic sources, such as alcohol-water mixtures and different types of fruit wines (Peppler & Beaman, 1967).

In general, it has been noted that the isolation and cultivation of *Acetobacter* species, particularly from fermented products like vinegar, can be challenging and frequently leads to an underestimating of the diversity of microbial species when culture-dependent approaches are used (Kittelman et al., 1989). According to Jara et al. (2013), the existence of viable but uncultivable organisms accounts in part for the low recovery of species. The creation of suitable media, which permitted the cultivation of slowly growing organisms, helped to some extent overcome the limitations of cultivation. Traditional culture media for isolating *Acetobacter* from various sources are described, with the primary carbon sources being glucose and ethanol. According to the ninth edition of Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology, the principal selection criteria of acetic acid-generating genera were Gram staining response, microscopic observation, catalase reaction, and oxidase reaction.

In the province of La Union, several vinegar producers can be found in various towns, specifically Naguilian, Agoo, and Luna. Their vinegar products were also known as "Sukang Iloko," also referred to in Ilocos Norte and Ilocos Sur.

Recently, no studies have been conducted to isolate the *Acetobacter* in their vinegar samples. Thus, research on the isolation, characterization, and application of *Acetobacter* vinegar from various producers in the province of La Union is essential and could make a significant contribution to the food and beverage industry in the area. Unlike its neighboring provinces, like Ilocos Norte and Ilocos Sur, research efforts were conducted in the research study of Franco and Gaoat (2020), which focused on the isolation, characterization, and utilization of *Acetobacter*.

The study is the first step in understanding the importance of isolating pure culture of *Acetobacter* species present in the sugarcane vinegar products of the province of La Union, as well as introducing to the local vinegar manufacturers to increase their vinegar production and enhance the quality of their sugarcane vinegar products in the future.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to isolate, characterize, and utilize *Acetobacter* species from the sugarcane vinegar product samples collected from different sugarcane vinegar manufacturers in the province of La Union.

Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. obtain sugarcane vinegar product samples in the province of La Union, specifically in the municipalities of Naguilian, Luna, and Agoo;
 2. evaluate the physicochemical characteristics of the sugarcane vinegar samples in terms of Brix, pH, and color;
 3. isolate putative *Acetobacter* species from five (5) different sugarcane vinegar product samples manufactured in La Union;
 4. characterize the *Acetobacter* isolates in terms of morphological (colony form, elevation, margin, pigment, bacterial shape, and arrangement), biochemical (Gram staining affinity, catalase test, and oxidase test), and physiological (isolates in given concentrations of Sodium acetate, ethanol, and glucose in the GYC medium and to a given levels of pH and temperature) traits;
 5. screen the *Acetobacter* isolates through the determination of the Potency Index (P.I.) and
 6. evaluate the *Acetobacter* isolates in terms of their effectiveness in producing vinegar with five (5) percent inoculum using fermented brown sugar solution.
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METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

Five (5) sugarcane vinegar product samples were obtained from the province of La Union, specifically in Naguilian, Luna, and Agoo municipalities. All the experimental procedures were done at the Laboratory of Molecular Microbiology and Biotechnology of the Mariano Marcos State University, City of Batac, Ilocos Norte.

Physicochemical Characteristics of the Sugarcane Vinegar Product Samples

The evaluation of the physicochemical characteristics of the sugarcane vinegar product samples was limited to the determination of °Brix, pH, and color using °Brix refractometer, pH meter, and color chart, respectively, for quality determination.

Isolation of *Acetobacter* species

In the isolation of *Acetobacter* species, one hundred (100) microliters of each of the vinegar product samples were inoculated using a micropipette (Dragon Lab, Model: YE3K109360) on the sterile Petri plates containing the solidified standard Glucose Yeast Calcium carbonate (GYC) agar medium. Inoculation was done through the pouring

method recommended by Cappuccino and Sherman (1996), and the inoculated vinegar product samples were spread evenly using a sterile spreader.

The isolation process used three replicates for each vinegar product sample. The Petri plate setups were labeled accordingly and were incubated (Labnet International Inc., Model: 211DS) at 30°C for ninety-six (96) hours. Arifuzzaman et al. (2014) claim that a clearing zone surrounding a bacterial colony is evidence that the colony comprises *Acetobacter* species.

Morphological and Biochemical Characterization of *Acetobacter* species

The bacterial colonies with clearing zones were characterized morphologically before isolation. Each bacterial colony with a clearing zone was morphologically characterized according to the colony form, elevation, margin, and pigment using a bacterial colony morphology chart.

After obtaining a pure culture of the putative *Acetobacter* isolates, biochemical tests were performed further to characterize the isolates, particularly the Gram staining affinity, which was determined through microscopic examination and to ascertain the bacterial shape and arrangement. The biochemical tests also included the catalase test and oxidase test, and each *Acetobacter* isolate was tested in three replicates for each test. The methods were adopted from the study of Ashcraft et al. (2001).

Physiological Characterization of *Acetobacter* species

Carbon sources. The growth of the *Acetobacter* isolates on different carbon sources was determined using sodium acetate, ethanol, and glucose added to the Glucose Yeast Calcium carbonate (GYC) agar medium. While the GYC medium was being prepared, a certain percentage of the carbon sources was added or adjusted. For sodium acetate, 2% was added to the GYC medium. For ethanol, an increase in 8%, 9%, and 10% was adjusted from the usual 7% added concentration of absolute ethanol to the GYC medium. The concentrations of 10%, 15%, and 20% for glucose were adjusted to the usual glucose concentration of the GYC medium to test the evident characteristics of the *Acetobacter* species. GYC agar plates were prepared and inoculated with *Acetobacter* by streaking, followed by incubation at 30°C for ninety-six (96) hours. All the setups were made with three replicates for each *Acetobacter* isolate. The suitability of these carbon sources for the growth of the isolates was observed and necessary as part of the characterization of *Acetobacter* species (Arifuzzaman et al., 2014; Kowser et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2015).

Temperature and pH. The growth of the *Acetobacter* isolates was subjected to different temperatures and pH levels. For the temperature, inoculation processes were made using the standard medium GYC agar plates by streak plate method of the *Acetobacter* isolates, and the different plate setups were incubated for the temperatures

of 25°C, 30°C, 35°C, and 40°C in the incubator (Labnet International Inc., Model: 211DS) for ninety-six (96) hours. After ninety-six (96) hours, the growth of bacterial isolates was observed, and the results were recorded.

Various pH levels were also used to test the pH tolerance of the isolates. The pH of the standard GYC medium was adjusted to the different pH setups (IQ Scientific Instruments, Model: IQ140). The pH setups performed were pH 3, pH 4, pH 5, pH 6, pH 7, and pH 8. The *Acetobacter* isolates were inoculated on the pH-adjusted GYC agar plates through the streak plate method. The Petri plates were incubated at 30°C for ninety-six (96) hours, and results were observed and recorded. For each *Acetobacter* isolate, three replicates were used in each setup (Arifuzzaman et al., 2014; Kowser et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2015).

Determination of Potency Index

The *Acetobacter* isolates underwent the Potency Index (P.I.) determination to determine the effectiveness of the isolates in producing acetic acid. A bacterial colony was spot-inoculated on the center of a GYC agar plate after being gathered with a sterile wire loop. Following the spot inoculation procedure, the Petri plates underwent a ninety-six (96) hour incubation at 30°C. After incubation, the GYC medium developed a clearing zone, which indicated acetic acid production. The *Acetobacter* colony and the clearing zone diameter were used to determine the potency of each isolate. The diameter of the clearing zone and the diameter of the colony formed by the *Acetobacter* isolates were measured in millimeters using a Vernier caliper. All the setups were made with three replicates for each *Acetobacter* isolate, and their average diameter of colony and clearing zone were calculated before the computation of the Potency Index. The formula below, adapted from the study of Arifuzzaman et al. (2014), was used to determine the Potency Index (P.I.) of the *Acetobacter* isolates.

$$P.I. = \frac{\text{Diameter of the Clearing Zone Formed}}{\text{Diameter of the Bacterial Colony}}$$

Evaluation of the Potential *Acetobacter* isolates for Acetic Acid Fermentation

The *Acetobacter* isolates were screened for their efficiency in vinegar production through fermentation. The experiment was a laboratory-scale activity wherein the *Acetobacter* isolates were tested for vinegar production using fermented brown sugar solution as the substrate. A two-way fermentation process had been followed. The first process was alcoholic fermentation using the brown sugar solution, while the second process was acetic acid fermentation, which converts alcohol into acetic acid using *Acetobacter* isolates.

Alcoholic fermentation. Twenty (20) °Brix (measured using a refractometer) was used as the initial sugar concentration of the brown sugar solution with the addition of 0.005% of instant yeast (Saf-instant; *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) per volume of the brown sugar solution. Using the Erlenmeyer flasks as a fermentation vessel with a cork cap and clear tubing attached and submerged in a bottle of water to release bubbles as a sign of fermentation, the fermentation process was completed once the generation of bubbles stopped. After the alcoholic fermentation, the fermented brown sugar juice was filtered twice using filter papers to remove the residues and the yeast that had settled on the bottom of the Erlenmeyer flask. Before the acetic acid fermentation, the °Brix, pH, and alcohol percentage of the fermented brown sugar solution were measured.

Preparation of *Acetobacter* inoculum. A test tube was filled with twenty (20) ml of Glucose Yeast (GY) broth before being filled with a loopful of the *Acetobacter* isolates and covered with a cotton plug. Before the fermentation of the acetic acid, the inoculum was cultured for five days at 30°C in an incubator (Labnet International Inc., Model: 211DS). Three replicates were used in each *Acetobacter* isolate setup.

Acetic acid fermentation. For the acetic acid fermentation, three hundred eighty (380) ml of filtered ethanolic brown sugar solution was equally distributed in every five hundred (500) ml sterilized glass jar. Twenty (20) ml of inoculum in Glucose Yeast (GY) broth (5% inoculum) of each *Acetobacter* isolate from the five (5) different vinegar manufacturers from the province of La Union was added to the fermentation glass jar with the filtered ethanolic solution making it a four hundred (400) ml of acetic acid fermentation setup. The fermentation glass jars were covered with sterilized white coarse fabrics or “katya” fastened with rubber bands for aerobic fermentation. Three (3) setups of acetic acid fermentation replicates were done for each *Acetobacter* isolate and three replicates for the control setup. In the control setup, four hundred (400) ml of filtered ethanolic solution are placed in a fermentation glass jar covered with sterilized white coarse fabrics or “katya” fastened with rubber bands. After completing the setup, the jars were stored in a sterile black container box at room temperature where light could not penetrate for three (3) months.

The pH and percent titrable acidity of each acetic acid fermentation setup with its three (3) replicates, including the control setup, were monitored and recorded every 30-day interval for three months from the day the setups were stored. The percent titrable acidity and pH of the acetic acid fermentation setup were measured by performing an acid-based titration method using a phenolphthalein indicator and calibrated pH meter (IQ Scientific Instruments, Model: IQ140), respectively. The fermentation technique was based on but modified from the research study by Fresco (2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Collection of Sugarcane Vinegar Product Samples in the Province of La Union

From the province of La Union, five (5) different sugarcane vinegar product samples were collected from five (5) sugarcane vinegar manufacturers in the municipalities of Naguilian, Luna, and Agoo.

For the study, manufacturer A was designated SV1; Manufacturer B was designated SV2; Manufacturer C was designated SV3; Manufacturer D was designated SV4, and Manufacturer E was designated SV5. The addresses of the five (5) sugarcane vinegar manufacturers were also noted.

Table 1. The vinegar manufacturers of the province of La Union.

Vinegar Samples	Manufacturers	Address
SV1	Manufacturer A	Doña Aida Dumpit Civic Center, Naguilian
SV2	Manufacturer B	Gusing Sur, Naguilian
SV3	Manufacturer C	Baraoas Road, Baraoas Norte, Naguilian
SV4	Manufacturer D	Luna-Balaoan-Bacnotan Road, Sto. Domingo Sur, Luna
SV5	Manufacturer E	Manila North Road, San Agustin Sur, Agoo

Table 1 reveals that most sugarcane manufacturers are located in the town of Naguilian; Manufacturer A, Manufacturer B and Manufacturer C. Manufacturer D is located in Sto. Domingo, Luna, La Union. Lastly, Manufacturer E is in San Agustin Sur, Agoo, La Union.

Physicochemical Characteristics of the Sugarcane Vinegar Product Samples

The physicochemical characteristics of all five (5) collected sugarcane vinegar product samples from different vinegar manufacturers in the province of La Union were analyzed.

The physicochemical parameters were limited to the °Brix, pH, and color. Measurement of °Brix is a metric for quantifying the number of solids dissolved in a liquid. It is frequently employed to assess the concentration of dissolved sugar in an aqueous solution. One °Brix corresponds to a concentration of 1 gram of sucrose per 100 grams of solution, indicating the mass percentage of the solution.

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of the sugarcane vinegar samples collected from different vinegar manufacturers in the province of La Union.

Vinegar Samples	°Brix	pH	Color
SV1	5.1	3.1	Golden Yellow
SV2	1.5	3.9	Golden Yellow
SV3	5.0	2.9	Golden Yellow
SV4	2.0	2.6	Brown
SV5	4.5	3.1	Brown

In Table 2, the physicochemical characteristics of the vinegar samples show that in terms of the sugar concentration, SV1 has the highest °Brix with 5.1, followed by SV3 with 5.0, SV5 with 4.5, SV4 with 2.0, and SV2 with the least sugar concentration of 1.5 °Brix, this shows that sugar is not fully converted into alcohol. The sugar concentration obtained varies from one vinegar to the other because they may have a different percentage of sugar concentration as the initial °Brix of the sugarcane juice at the start of the alcoholic fermentation. Also, the fermenting organisms that might be present had affected the fermentation, which could result in the presence of sugar concentration in the vinegar as the final product. A pH meter is an instrument that assesses the acidity or alkalinity of a solution or sample by measuring the activity of Hydrogen ions. In the pH readings of the different vinegar samples, SV2 had the highest pH of 3.9, followed by SV1 and SV5 with the same pH of 3.1, followed by SV3 with a pH of 2.9, and SV4 with a pH of 2.6, the most acidic.

According to Fresco (2011) and Rotor (2022), the color of “Sukang Iloko,” or sugarcane vinegar, ranges from dark brown to golden yellow. The color of the vinegar depends on the sugarcane variety used, the age of the vinegar, and also the material being used to store the samples for vinegar. The color of the SV1, SV2, and SV3 vinegar product samples is golden yellow. Lastly, brown color was observed in SV4 and SV5. All the findings of the physicochemical characteristics of the different sugarcane vinegar samples conform with the sugarcane vinegar characteristics presented by Fresco (2011) and Rotor (2022). *Acetobacter* species are considered to be present if a sugar content is present, and they convert the ethanol to acetic acid in the vinegar, resulting in a low pH and high acidity (Lee et al., 2015). According to Sharafi et al. (2010), some *Acetobacter* species, such as *Acetobacter pasteurianus* strains, can produce acetic acid from ethanol and glucose.

***Acetobacter* species Isolated from Five (5) Sugarcane Vinegar Product Samples in the Province of La Union**

In the isolation process of *Acetobacter*, the clearing zone surrounding the bacterial colony on a GYC agar plate indicates a putative *Acetobacter* species (Arifuzzaman et al., 2014).

Table 3. *Acetobacter* isolates obtained from the vinegar product samples.

Vinegar Samples	Replicates	No. of Isolates	Isolate Code
SV1	R1	0	-
	R2	1	<i>a</i>
	R3	1	<i>b</i>
SV2	R1	1	<i>c</i>
	R2	0	-
	R3	0	-
SV3	R1	0	-
	R2	0	-
	R3	1	<i>d</i>
SV4	R1	0	-
	R2	1	<i>e</i>
	R3	0	-
SV5	R1	1	<i>f</i>
	R2	0	-
	R3	0	-

The clearing zone shows the acetic acid production by *Acetobacter* species (Sharafi et al., 2010). The reaction of acetic acid produced by the bacteria and Calcium carbonate in the mixture of the GYC agar produces Calcium acetate, water, and Carbon dioxide (Sudsakda et al., 2007).

As presented in Table 3, there are six (6) bacterial isolates presumptively identified as *Acetobacter* species isolated from the five (5) sugarcane vinegar product samples as their distinguishing characteristics, the clearing zone, are evident on the Glucose Yeast Calcium carbonate (GYC) agar plates. Among the five (5) vinegar product samples, there are two (2) isolates from SV1 which were coded as *a* and *b*, and one (1) isolate each from SV2, SV3, SV4, and SV5, and were coded as *c*, *d*, *e*, and *f*, respectively. The study used the isolated *Acetobacter* species in the characterization, screening, and utilization processes.

Morphological Characteristics of the Isolated *Acetobacter* species

The colony morphology was determined in form, margin, elevation, and pigment. The bacterial shapes and arrangement were also observed using a microscope.

Table 4. Morphological characteristics of the *Acetobacter* isolates.

Isolates	Colony Characteristics			Pigment	Shape	Arrangement
	Form	Elevation	Margin			
<i>a</i>	Circular	Raised	Entire	Off white	Rod	Singly, or short-chain
<i>b</i>	Irregular	Flat	Undulate	Off white	Rod	Single
<i>c</i>	Irregular	Flat	Undulate	Pinkish white	Rod	Single
<i>d</i>	Circular	Convex	Entire	Creamy white	Rod	Singly, or short-chain
<i>e</i>	Circular	Convex	Entire	Pinkish white	Rod	Singly, or short-chain
<i>f</i>	Circular	Raised	Entire	Creamy white	Rod	Singly, or short-chain

The morphological characteristics of the *Acetobacter* isolates are displayed in Table 4. The form, elevation, margin, and pigment of the colony of the *Acetobacter* isolates were examined using a bacterial colony morphology reference chart. The isolates

b and *c* exhibit irregular, flat, and undulate forms, elevations, and margins. The colony characteristics of isolates *a* and *f* were identical, characterized by a circular shape, raised elevation, and entire margin. The isolates *d* and *e* exhibit identical colony characteristics, characterized by a circular shape, convex elevation, and an entire margin. The pigment of isolates *a* and *b* is a shade of off-white, whereas isolates *c* and *e* have a pinkish-white pigment, and isolates *d* and *f* have a creamy white pigment.

Figure 1: *Acetobacter* Isolates *a*, *b*, *c*, *d*, *e*, and *f*.

Figure 1 shows the colony images of *Acetobacter* isolates *a*, *b*, *c*, *d*, *e*, and *f* from the five (5) sugarcane vinegar product samples collected from the different sugarcane vinegar manufacturers in La Union. Notice the clearing zone surrounding the colonies, a unique characteristic of *Acetobacter* species.

All the *Acetobacter* isolates are rod-shaped, which is a distinguishing characteristic among all *Acetobacter* in terms of bacterial shape (Lee et al., 2015). Isolates *b* and *c* are single in arrangement, while the other isolates are singly or in short chains. The bacterial shape and arrangement matched the research studies of Yamada et al. (1999), Ashecraft et al. (2001), and Zahoor et al. (2006).

Biochemical Characteristics of the Isolated *Acetobacter* species

Biochemical characterization is essential in determining *Acetobacter* species, primarily in Gram staining reactions, catalase, and oxidase tests (Buchanan & Gibbons, 1984).

Table 5. Biochemical characteristics of the *Acetobacter* isolates.

Isolates	Gram Staining Affinity*	Catalase test**	Oxidase test**
<i>a</i>	-	+	-
<i>b</i>	-	+	-
<i>c</i>	-	+	-
<i>d</i>	-	+	-
<i>e</i>	-	+	-
<i>f</i>	-	+	-

Legend: * (-) Gram negative ** (+) positive; (-) negative

Table 5 shows the biochemical characteristics of the isolated *Acetobacter* species, specifically with the Gram staining affinity, catalase test, and oxidase test being the parameters that were tested.

Gram staining reaction determines whether bacteria are Gram-positive, as they appear blue to violet, or Gram-negative, as they appear red to pink. In this study, all the *Acetobacter* isolates are Gram-negative. They appear to be pink in color after performing the Gram staining activity, which is a characteristic among all *Acetobacter*, as stated by Andres-Barrao et al. (2012), Arifuzzaman et al. (2014), and Lee et al. (2015).

The catalase test determines that certain bacteria can synthesize the enzyme catalase by degrading the hydrogen peroxide to water and oxygen. The presence of bubbles in the bacteria, when dropped with hydrogen peroxide, reveals a positive result. All isolates are catalase test positive, another characteristic among all *Acetobacter* species studied by Andres-Barrao et al. (2012) and Arifuzzaman et al. (2014).

Another biochemical test conducted was the oxidase test. All the *Acetobacter* species have a negative oxidase test result. Results show that they cannot synthesize the enzyme oxidase. The oxidase test determines which bacteria generate cytochrome c

oxidase, an enzyme of the bacterial electron transport chain. All oxidase-positive bacteria can utilize oxygen as a terminal electron acceptor during respiration since they are all aerobic. They are not necessarily strict aerobes. According to the Michigan State University Virtual Interactive Laboratory, oxidase-negative bacteria can be facultative, anaerobic, or both. The result indicates that these organisms lack the cytochrome c oxidase necessary to oxidize the test reagent. They might use alternative oxidases for electron transport during respiration. A positive result dictates a change of color of the oxidase testing reagent when dropped on the bacterial smear from black to purple. When the color remains black, it means negative. All of the *Acetobacter* isolates are oxidase test-negative. The negative oxidase test of all *Acetobacter* isolates follows the study of Arifuzzaman et al. (2014), who found that one distinct characteristic of *Acetobacter* is that it is oxidase-negative.

Growth of *Acetobacter* Isolates on GYC agar containing different Carbon Sources

In the studies of Adachi et al. (2003), Arifuzzaman et al. (2014), and Lee et al. (2015), they characterized the isolated *Acetobacter* species employing their growth in different carbon sources. *Acetobacter* species can withstand or grow among several carbon sources, such as different ethanol, glucose, and sodium acetate concentrations.

Table 6. Growth of *Acetobacter* isolates on GYC agar containing carbon sources.

Isolates	Ethanol			Glucose			Sodium Acetate
	8%	9%	10%	10%	15%	20%	2%
<i>a</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>b</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>c</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>d</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>e</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>f</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Legend: (+) with growth

Concentrations of carbon sources used in the *Acetobacter* species added or adjusted in the GYC agar were 8%, 9%, and 10% ethanol; 10%, 15%, and 20% glucose; and 2% sodium acetate. Table 6 shows that all *Acetobacter* isolates can grow at different concentrations of carbon sources in the GYC agar with clearing zones surrounding their colony.

The findings show that all the *Acetobacter* isolates can withstand high concentrations of ethanol and glucose because the concentrations used are higher than the recommended concentration to be added in the formulation of the GYC medium. These results conform with the research of Adachi et al. (2003), Arifuzzaman et al. (2014),

and Lee et al. (2015) in their physiological characterization studies on the growth of *Acetobacter* species to different carbon sources. The addition of 2% sodium acetate in the GYC medium also shows that the isolates were able to grow, as this parameter is essential for the characterization of an unknown *Acetobacter* species (Arifuzzaman et al., 2014).

Growth of the Isolated *Acetobacter* species on Different Temperatures and pH levels

The optimum temperature for *Acetobacter* species to grow ranges from 28-30°C, known as mesophilic (Saeki et al., 1997; Sudsakda et al., 2007; Sengun & Karabiyikli, 2011). However, some species are recognized as thermotolerant and can grow to 37-40°C (Adachi et al., 2003).

Table 7. The growth of the isolated *Acetobacter* species at different temperatures.

Isolates	Temperatures			
	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
<i>a</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>b</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>c</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>d</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>e</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>f</i>	+	+	+	+

Legend: (+) with growth

Table 7 presents the results of the growth of *Acetobacter* isolates at different temperatures. The isolated *Acetobacter* species were incubated for ninety-six (96) hours at 25°C, 30°C, 35°C, and 40°C using the GYC medium to observe the presence or absence of growth as an indicator for the *Acetobacter* isolates and to determine if they had tolerated the specified temperature which they had been exposed.

The result of this screening shows that all the isolated *Acetobacter* species were able to grow from temperatures 25-40°C and are considered thermotolerant with 30°C as the temperature where the clearing zones and growth of all *Acetobacter* isolates were more prominent and distinguishable. As the temperature increases to 40°C or decreases to 25°C, the size of clearing zones is noticeably decreasing. Arifuzzaman et al. (2014) and Lee et al. (2015) observed a similar effect of temperature to their isolated *Acetobacter* species.

Table 8. The growth of the isolated *Acetobacter* species at different pH levels.

Isolates	pH levels					
	3	4	5	6	7	8
<i>a</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>b</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>c</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>d</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>e</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>f</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+

Legend: (+) with growth

The pH can be a crucial factor in the production of vinegar, so there is a need to determine the pH tolerance of the bacterial isolates in terms of their growth as an indicator using different pH levels (3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8). Generally, the optimum pH for the growth of *Acetobacter* species ranges from 5 to 6, while they can grow at a lower pH, which ranges from 3 to 4 (Du Toit & Pretorius, 2002; Sengun & Karabiyikli, 2011).

Results revealed in Table 8 that all the isolated *Acetobacter* species could grow at pH 3 to 8. The findings are similar to the results obtained by the study of Arifuzzaman et al. (2014) and Lee et al. (2015) on the effect of different pH levels on the growth of *Acetobacter* species. The results show that the isolated *Acetobacter* species are considered acidophilic since they can grow from pH 3 to 6 and withstand pH 8 at the basic pH level.

Potency Index Determination of the *Acetobacter* Isolates

The determination of the Potency Index (P.I.) was used as the main criterion in assessing the acetic acid production of the *Acetobacter* isolates, as shown by the clearing zone surrounding the colony growth. The sizes of clearing zones reveal the strength of each strain of *Acetobacter* (Sharafi et al., 2010). The six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates underwent a Potency Index (P.I.) determination to ascertain their ability to produce acetic acid.

Table 9. Average Potency Index and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Potency Index of the *Acetobacter* isolates in millimeters (mm).

Isolates	Diameter Size of the Colony (mm)	Size of Clearing Zone (mm)	Potency Index (P.I.) (mm)
<i>a</i>	11.49	33.23	2.89 ^{bc}
<i>b</i>	11.32	26.38	2.33 ^c

<i>c</i>	23.55	36.70	1.59 ^d
<i>d</i>	13.14	17.76	1.35 ^d
<i>e</i>	11.25	38.09	3.41 ^{ab}
<i>f</i>	11.41	46.13	4.05 ^a
Significance			**
CV (%)			9.19

Legend: ** - highly significant at 1% level of significance

From the Potency Index determination procedure, after ninety-six (96) hours of incubation, the diameter of the clearing zone produced by the *Acetobacter* isolates and the diameter of the *Acetobacter* colony were measured. The isolate is more likely to produce a large amount of acetic acid if the clearing zone is large, whereas it is more likely to produce a small amount of acetic acid if the clearing zone is small (Sharafi et al., 2010; Arifuzzaman et al., 2014). The formula, modified from Arifuzzaman et al. (2014) was used to calculate the Potency Index of *Acetobacter* isolates as presented in the methodology.

Table 9 shows the average Potency Index of the isolates in millimeters after ninety-six (96) hours of incubation. The size of the clearing zone produced by the *Acetobacter* isolates indicates their efficiency in acetic acid production. The result shows that out of six (6) isolates, Isolate *f* from SV5 produced the largest size of clearing zone with 46.13 mm, followed by Isolate *e* with a clearing zone of 38.09mm, *c* with 36.70 mm, *a* with 33.23 mm, *b* with 26.38, and the least is Isolate *d* with a clearing zone size of 17.76 mm.

Regarding the computed Potency Index, the results also follow the arrangement in terms of the size of the clearing zone, except for Isolate *c*, wherein Isolate *f* has the highest computed Potency Index of 4.05. At the same time, Isolate *d* produced the lowest computed index with 1.35mm, which shows that the isolates vary in terms of their efficiency in acetic acid production. The results showed that Isolate *f* has the foremost result among the other isolates in the Potency Index determination, which means it has excellent potential in vinegar production.

Table 9 also presents the result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the data gathered in the Potency Index determination using STAR software. Results reveal that for the Potency Index of the six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates, the data are highly significant at the 1% significance level, meaning that the *Acetobacter* isolates differ in their Potency Index. They are highly significant because of the p-value. The critical value is also low, which means the data or the values are close to each other because the critical value or CV tells how dispersed the values produced by the *Acetobacter* isolates are. Overall, isolate *f*, which obtained the highest value for the Potency Index, is the best among the

other isolates because it shows the larger clearing zone produced in terms of its diameter and Potency Index.

According to the study of Arifuzzaman et al. (2014), in the “Isolation and Characterization of *Acetobacter* and *Gluconobacter* species from Sugarcane and Rotten Fruits,” the isolates produce more acetic acid if a higher Potency Index value was obtained. As a result, the Potency Index activity showed how potently an *Acetobacter* species can produce acetic acid.

Screening for Acetic Acid Production

The pH level and titrable acidity percentage were tracked for three (3) consecutive months from the day of setting up for the acetic acid fermentation to ascertain the acetic acid production of the six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates and the control setup.

Table 10. Average pH Level and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the pH.

Isolates	First Month	Second Month	Third Month
<i>a</i>	3.40 ^a	3.43 ^{ab}	3.2
<i>b</i>	3.40 ^a	3.40 ^b	3.0
<i>c</i>	3.43 ^a	3.40 ^b	3.23
<i>d</i>	3.40 ^a	3.40 ^b	3.6
<i>e</i>	3.40 ^a	3.50 ^a	3.07
<i>f</i>	3.47 ^a	3.40 ^{ab}	3.53
Control (-)	3.30 ^b	3.43 ^{ab}	3.17
Significance	**	*	ns
CV (%)	0.9804	0.9382	9.91

Legend: ** - highly significant at 1% level of significance

* - significant at a 5% level of significance

ns - not significant

note: means with the same letter are not significantly different

The substrate used for the acetic acid fermentation was the brown sugar solution that had fermented during the ethanolic fermentation. The °Brix, pH, and alcohol percentage of the ethanolic brown sugar solution were measured. The °Brix is 6.2, pH at 3.6, and the 4.2% for the alcohol content. Table 10 shows the average pH level of the acetic acid fermentation setups. During the initial month of pH level monitoring, most *Acetobacter* vinegar setups exhibited a pH value of 3.4. The pH of the control setup was 3.3 in the first month and 3.43 in the second month. During the second month of pH screening, the pH levels of the *Acetobacter* vinegar setups generally remained within the range of 3.4, except for the isolate *e* fermentation setup. The pH levels of all the setups decreased during the third month of pH level screening, compared to the first and second months, except for isolates *d* and *f*. The reason may be attributed to the characteristics

of the isolates, as they are different from each other. After three months of acetic acid fermentation, the pH obtained from the samples shows that Isolate *b* obtained the lowest pH at 3.0, becoming the most acidic, followed by Isolate *e* at 3.07.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of pH level obtained from the acetic acid fermentation setup screening by the *Acetobacter* isolates using 5% inoculum is also shown in Table 10. The statistical analysis was done as a whole, meaning the data obtained from all the isolates for the first, second, and third months are not per isolate. The Analysis of Variance indicates that the pH level between the isolates and the control in the first month of acetic acid fermentation is highly significant at the 1% significance level. However, on average, those with the same letter are not significantly different. On the other hand, the pH level in the second month of acetic acid fermentation indicates that the control is significantly different at the 5% significance level. Furthermore, for the third month, the analysis showed that the pH of the isolates, including the control, was not significantly different, which means there were no differences in the pH obtained by the isolates compared to the control.

Table 11. Average Titrable Acidity Level and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the Titrable Acidity.

Isolates	First Month	Second Month	Third Month
<i>a</i>	5.6	5.0	5.8
<i>b</i>	5.2	5.0	6.0
<i>c</i>	5.2	5.2	5.6
<i>d</i>	5.2	5.4	5.6
<i>e</i>	5.2	5.0	5.6
<i>f</i>	5.6	5.6	5.8
Control (-)	4.0	4.8	5.6
Significance	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)	17.2	16.17	6.9

Legend: ns – not significant

The average percentage of titrable acidity for all acetic acid production setups was presented in Table 11; in the first month, it had reached 5.0% acidity, with Isolates *a* and *f* having the highest titrable acidity at 5.6%. The titrable acidity of the control setup was only 4.0%. All setups maintain the titrable acidity at the 5.0% range in the second month of screening and 4.8% for the control setup. During the third month, the titrable acidity percentage of all the setups, including the control, increased, ranging from 5.6 to 6.0% for the *Acetobacter* acetic acid fermentation setups, with Isolate *b* having the highest titrable acidity at 6.0%, followed by Isolates *a* and *f* at 5.8%. The percentage of titrable acidity in the control setup is 5.6 compared to 4.0 and 4.8 in the first and second months of titrable acidity screenings, respectively.

The result of acetic acid fermentation in terms of percentage titrable acidity and pH is that every month, the percentage of acidity increases as the pH level decreases and gets more acidic. In connection with the Potency Index determination of the *Acetobacter* isolates and their Analysis of Variance, the acetic acid production screening results showed that, after just one month of acetic acid fermentation, the *Acetobacter* vinegar setups reached 5.0% acidity. In contrast, the control only reached 4.0% acidity. As stated by Joyeux et al. (1984), Drysdale and Fleet (1985), and Kocher et al. (2006), vinegar is a solution with a 5% concentration of acetic acid, and this means that the six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates can produce vinegar within one (1) month period as seen in the results of the average titrable acidity.

Therefore, after three months of acetic acid fermentation, among the isolates, Isolate *b* produced the highest computed percent titrable acidity at 6.0% as compared to the control. The result coincides with the average pH obtained by the isolates, wherein *b* produced the lowest pH, the most acidic after three (3) months of acetic acid fermentation. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the acidity obtained from the screening of the *Acetobacter* isolates is also shown in Table 11. The data are generally analyzed per month. The result indicates that the percentage acidity among the *Acetobacter* vinegar setups on the first, second, and third months of screening for acetic acid fermentation is similar. With these findings, all the *Acetobacter* isolates can be utilized for vinegar production as they produce acetic acid. Overall, Isolate *b* had the best performance for acetic acid fermentation among the six isolates obtained from the sugarcane vinegar product samples produced in the province of La Union.

Conclusions

Six putative *Acetobacter* isolates were identified from the five sugarcane vinegar product samples, producing clearing zones around their colonies, indicating acetic acid production. They are Gram-negative bacteria. The *Acetobacter* isolates are catalase test positive, indicating their ability to synthesize the enzyme, and oxidase test negative, indicating their ability to use alternative oxidases for electron transport during respiration.

The *Acetobacter* isolates had endured a high concentration of ethanol and glucose, exceeding the recommended amount in the GYC medium formulation. The addition of 2% sodium acetate also allowed the isolates to grow. These are crucial parameters for the characterization of unknown *Acetobacter*.

The study reveals that the isolated *Acetobacter* are thermotolerant, growing from 25-40°C. The isolated *Acetobacter* species exhibited the highest amount of acetic acid production in pH 5 and pH 6, as they produced a larger clearing zone.

The study found that Isolate *f*, with the highest Potency Index of 4.05, has the highest potential for vinegar production among six isolates after four days of incubation. It was considered the foremost among the isolates due to its larger clearing zone. The findings demonstrated variations in the Potency Index results of the *Acetobacter* isolates, with the data being highly significant at the 1% significance level.

In the acetic acid fermentation, after the first month of screening, the pH had decreased more in the third month compared to the first and second months, making the acetic acid fermentation setups more acidic. In the first month of titrable acidity screening, it was found that the acetic acid fermentation setups inoculated with the *Acetobacter* isolates reached 5% acidity, which means that the setups are now considered sugarcane vinegar. The percentage of titrable acidity of the *Acetobacter* acetic acid fermentation setups increased in the third month, ranging from 5.6 to 6.0%.

It is therefore concluded that the six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates are highly recommendable and promising for acetic acid vinegar fermentation to increase the number of vinegar production and quality within one (1) month duration, based on the findings in the Potency Index determination and the acetic acid fermentation screening of the activity of the *Acetobacter* isolates. Moreover, it is also concluded that as the pH level of the acetic acid fermentation process decreases, the percentage of titrable acidity increases.

Recommendations

The findings of the study led to the proposal of the recommendations: First, to further validate the identity of these promising isolates, the six (6) *Acetobacter* isolates need to undergo molecular identification using 16S rRNA. Second, utilizing pure and fresh sugarcane juice extract (binnal) as the fermentation substrate is recommended for future studies. Additionally, conducting a range-finder test is recommended in addition to other characterization procedures and physiological testing to identify distinct species of *Acetobacter*. Lastly, the pure culture of the *Acetobacter* isolates must be introduced to the local vinegar manufacturers, especially to the Province of La Union, to increase their vinegar production and to enhance the quality of their sugarcane vinegar products in the future and as a starter culture or additional supplement to the mother vinegar.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was carried out very strictly according to ethical research guidelines. The researchers declare that the way this study is conducted shows no conflict of interest. Every required step was taken to guarantee that plagiarism was absolutely avoided and correct references were given to credit pertinent sources. Furthermore, the way the results were interpreted was objective, so guaranteeing that no prejudice affected them. Maintaining integrity and objectivity throughout the research, the results of this study were used just for scholarly and investigative needs.

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